

Customer response Analysis in Chili Value Addition: A Success Story of Khairpur Mirs Sindh-Pakistan

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Abstract:

This research investigates the Customer Response Analysis in Chili Value Addition: A Success story of Khairpur Mirs Sindh-Pakistan. Data were collected from different display centers Kumb District Khairpur Mirs. A structural questionnaire was design for the reliability and validity of data. The methodology applied is based on the value chain approach. It focuses on the detailed mapping on all levels of the chain, from the functions and actors on the micro level to partners and support institutions on a massive level, up to rules and regulations having influence on the value chain on a macro level. It was revealed that The farmers have various problems like low price, heavy commission charges, the lack of finance, non- availability of manures, pesticides, water scarcity, the lack of storage facilities, high transport cost, the lack of regular payment and the like. They are analysed with the help of ranking technology.

Key words: Chili, Growers, value Addition, Khairpur Mirs

Introduction:

In Sindh, chillies are developed on a territory of 38.4 thousand hectares with creation of 80,000 tons. Sindh contributes around 85 percent to red chilli production in Pakistan. The normal yield of 1.7 tons per hectare contributes 1.5 percent to the nation's GDP. Crisp dominant part of new bean stew is sold on the household advertise instead of being sent out. The most essential market is Sukkur District, however some littler markets in various zones of Kumb Khairpur Mirs move new bean stew in constrained amounts. By far most of the new stew sold in Sukkur, is exchanged first through the canter man. Centre man got half of their pay just to encourage the ranchers by giving them advances their fundamental needs. The bean stew is sourced from all stew developing regions, contingent upon the accessibility of bean stew. The wholesalers exchange in excess of 10 distinct assortments. Retailers purchase specifically from this discount market and exchange to eateries, shops and little markets. The piece of the pie of crisp bean stew is little contrasted with that of dried stew and the time span of usability is restricted to 3-4 days, making the item very touchy.

Literature Review

G.F Antonious, J.E. Meyer, J.A Rogers and Y. Hu (2007) agriculturists around the globe gives a pesticide that can be utilized to bar the quantity of nuisances and creepy crawlies. Pepper (annum) as natural pesticides has a possibility to control the most astounding amount of bugs and to have a most elevated rate of harvest generation. Thus, it can help to the rapidly development of strands and plants. Today, stew pepper (capsicum annum) develop generally in numerous parts of the world as an essential business edits that can be tried to deliver a natural pesticides without awful impact to the wellbeing of the general population and furthermore that is eco-accommodating.

The insecticidal capability of stew pepper leaf separates against termites

As indicated by Romano (nd) bean stew is pointedly enhanced product of a pepper plant that can be tested as pesticides. Insecticidal stew pepper (capsicum annum) can possibly lessen the quantity of termites that devastates furniture or anything made of wood and furthermore different creepy crawlies bugs. Then again, bean stew pepper (capsicum annum) as everybody knows it, is a most loved flavor of numerous individuals

around the globe including the Philippines. In opposite, stew (capsicum) additionally contains a characteristic certainties and wellbeing profiting properties that can be utilized as useful medications. Despite its fiery taste, it is truly practicable to vanquish LDL cholesterol levels in corpulent people. Bean stew pepper (capsicum annum) has incredibly abnormal amounts of nutrients and minerals.

Nourishment Facts of Chili Pepper

Stew peppers (capsicum annum), in spite of their red hot hotness, are one of the exceptionally mainstream flavors known for their restorative and wellbeing profiting properties. The bean stew really, is a natural product unit from the plant having a place with the nightshade family (Solenceae), inside the sort, capsicum. (Berke and Shieh, 2000)

Medical advantages of Chili Pepper

Chilies, contains wellbeing profiting alkaloid compound like capsaicin, which gives them solid zesty sharp character. Crisp bean stew peppers, red and green, are rich wellspring of nutrient C. 100g crisp chilies give about 143.7g about 240% of RDA. Nutrient C is a strong water-solvent cancer prevention agent. It is requires for the collagen amalgamation inside the human body. They are additionally great in different cancer prevention agents, for example, nutrient An, and flavonoids like B-carotene, a-carotene, lutein, zea-xanthin, and cryptoxanthin. These cell reinforcements substances in capsicum help shield the body from harmful impacts of free radicals produced amid pressure, ailments conditions. (USDA National Nutrient information base)

Chilies convey a decent measure of minerals like potassium, manganese, iron, and magnesium. Potassium is a critical part of a cell and body liquids that enables controlling heart to rate and circulatory strain. Manganese is utilized by the body as a co-factor for the cancer prevention agents catalyst, superoxide dismutase. Chilies are likewise great in B-complex gathering of nutrients, for example, niacin, pyridoxine (nutrient B-6) riboflavin and thiamin (nutrient B-1). These nutrients are basic as in human body requires them from outer sources to renew. (USDA National Nutrient information base)

Advantage of utilizing Chili Pepper to the Low-salary Farmers

As per Gianessi and Williams (2012) bean stew pepper (capsicum annum) is extremely prominent in each nation, including India. Three-fourths of India's agriculturist had use bean stew (capsicum) as pesticides to ensure or even secure the specific dimension of harvest yield. Furthermore, it can likewise limit danger of product disappointment and misfortunes and to drain the higher number of creepy crawly bugs, for example, borers, thrips and so forth additionally, it gives gigantic advantage of utilizing pesticides incorporate expanded sustenance creation, expanded benefits for ranchers and the avoidance of sicknesses. (Ahmed, 2010)

Expanded Food Production

As the human populace builds, the measure of sustenance created is critical. Because of the high loss of sustenance creation, pesticides are frequently used to attempt to battle the issue. By the assistance of bean stew pepper pesticides, it is conceivable to diminish the quantity of irritations and deliver bigger amounts of sustenance.

Expanded Profits for Farmers

In utilizing pesticides, agriculturists can delivered more harvests that can expand benefits by having more create to move. Pesticides likewise expanded homestead benefits by helping the agriculturist get a good deal on work costs. Utilizing pesticides, it decreases the measure of time required to physically expel weeds and irritations from fields. (Kenya, Ghana, 2007)

Counteractive action of Diseases

Sparing products and domesticated animals, pesticides have additionally an immediate advantage to human wellbeing. It is assessed that since 1945, the utilization of pesticide has kept the passings of around seven million individuals by executing nuisances that convey or transmit ailment. Jungle fever, which is transmitted by tainted mosquitoes, is a standout amongst the most generally known and dangerous infections that has diminished in pervasiveness because of the utilization of pesticides.

These characteristic pesticides used to repulse and dispose of hurtful nuisance. The bean stew pepper (*capsicum annum*) remove can possibly use as a natural pesticides that can dispense with the high number of nuisances. Common pesticides can battle creepy crawlies upon contact or through ingestion. Use as a feature of an incorporated Pest Management Program which incorporates snares for checking and catching irritations and advantageous creepy crawlies and living beings to control bugs in their creating stages. Upgrading richness programs with characteristic manures and soil alterations will build plants' wellbeing and protection from a wide range of nuisances in your home or cultivating including weeds and infections. (Kumar et al., 2009)

Hypothetical Framework

Lichtenberg and Zilberman (1986) gave a hypothetical establishment on why pesticides are defensive sources of info and not profitable contributions as regularly saw in past examinations. Pesticides give a noteworthy commitment to edit creation just if a genuine vermin assault exists and if the pesticides use can control the bug assault viably. In the event that ranchers don't watch the vermin assault, all things considered, they may not make a difference pesticides by any stretch of the imagination. Adjusting the idea of monetary edge n utilization of pesticides is recommended by Headley (1972) and Mumford and Norton (1984) we have broke down the components deciding Indonesian bean stew ranchers choice on the dimension of pesticides.

Ranchers' targets for plant insurance are not exclusively to get high return yet in addition to limit danger of harvest disappointment and to guarantee monetary effectiveness of homestead inputs utilized, including pesticides synthetic compounds. This is clarified by the idea of financial limit for both the amount just as the power of utilization. The financial edge is characterized as: For any dimension of vermin assault a most extreme satisfactory dimension of bug assault for which the normal estimation of yield misfortune related with the irritation is equivalent to the expense of nuisance control estimates utilizing pesticides. (Headley, 1972; Mariyono, 2007)

Methodology

Data were collected from 300 customers in Kumb District Khairpur Mirs. A structural poll were plan for the dependability and legitimacy of information. The technique connected depends on the esteem chain approach. It centers around the point by point mapping on all dimensions of the chain, from the capacities and on-screen characters on the miniaturized scale level to accomplices and bolster organizations on a mass level, up to standards and controls having effect on the esteem chain on a large scale level.

A total of 14 value added products were developed and displayed including green chili chutney, green chili powder, green chilli flakes, green chilli tomato powder, chili pickle, chilli ketchup, tomato jam, onion pickle, onion chilli mixed pickle, onion powder, onion flakes, potato kheer and potato powder.

SWOT Analysis

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
Value addition Products are better in quality and taste. Customers satisfied Efficient farmers	Limited Stock available Lack of market Access
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Explore New markets Increase market value Faster growing market	Competitive market. Price variation

Results

All the chose dry bean stew cultivators were met for the issues they are confronting while at the same time creating and advertising of significant worth expansion of bean stew. The data with respect to the vital issues looked by the producers is exhibited in Table 1.

The agriculturists have different issues like low value, overwhelming commission charges, the absence of back, non-accessibility of composts, pesticides, water shortage, the absence of storerooms, high transport cost, the absence of customary installment and so forth. They are investigated with the assistance of positioning innovation.

**According to the customer response Analysis
Total Sample size=300**

Variables	Products	1 Strongly Agreed	2 Agreed	3 Neither	4 Disagree	5 Strongly Disagree
Quality	Green Chili Chutney	200	70	30	0	
Taste	Green Chilli Flakes,	200	70	20	10	
Labels & Packages	Green Chili Powder	200	70	20	10	
Taste Difference	Green Chilli	250	50	0	0	
Perceive value	Onion Chilli Mixed Pickle,	200	70	30	0	
Which media channel you prefer	Chili Pickle	200	70	20	10	
Electronic		200	70	20	10	
Print		200	70	20	10	
Billboard		200	70	20	10	
Price		200	70	30	0	
Compare to Market Price		250	250	0	10	
How often you used these Products		200	70	20	10	
Innovation		200	70	20	10	
Lack of Financial Facility		200	70	20	10	
		200	70	20	10	

The present investigation was led in Kumb District Khairpur Mirs. Requirements discovered amid pre-testing organized. Important data was gathered through a review technique with the assistance of pre-tried poll. The

recurrence and level of every limitation were worked out to gauge the requirements experienced by the respondents. Based on results got from the examination, following ends are drawn.

Conclusions:

The current study focus on Chillies value addition in Kumb Khairpur Mirs the main objectives of this study that how our project make innovation in different vegetables in loung Khan soomro. We have analysed how to use of Chiullies for the betterment and improve livelihood and income for the small farmers. The Lack of specialized information was serious issue underway which was communicated by 81 ranchers. Absence of money related office it was communicated by 79 dry stew cultivators and need. The Lack of technical knowledge was major problem in production which was expressed by 200 farmers. Lack of financial facility it was expressed chilli growers and lack of drying space for red chilli which was expressed by 78 farmers. In regarding to marketing of dry chilli non-remunerative price of dry chilli and high cost of transportation and heavy commission charges as reported by farmers, happened to be the major problems which was expressed by the chili farmers

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